

Study and Creating E-Governance Storyboards using features of Tableau Software

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Abstract— This paper explores using Tableau Software to create e-governance storyboards, using features of Tableau Software. It details methods for transforming complex data into visual narratives, showcases case studies, and highlights Tableau's impact on public service efficiency. Findings suggest Tableau significantly improves data analysis and presentation, offering best practices for optimizing e-governance initiatives.

Even though an abstract goes at the beginning of the work, it acts as a summary of the entire report. Rather than introducing the topic, it will be an overview of everything that has been written in the paper.

In the first part of the paper, we have studied extensively the different features of Tableau Software required to create E-Governance Story-boards.

Then, we have focused on how E-Governance story-boards can be represented using worksheets and dashboards. In this project, we primarily focused on three measuring options –

1. Geographic measure, 2.Population measure, 3.House-type measure.

In the first measure, we have used features for geographic representation of Tableau to show the districts and blocks of a particular state in a 'filled polygon' form. In our project, we have dealt with the state of West Bengal and one of its districts, South 24 Parganas. After building the filled polygons for the districts of West Bengal, we have created the blocks of the district South 24 Parganas.

In the second measure, we have depicted how to deal with the different population measures state-wise, district-wise, block-wise, area-wise. The population measures include Age wise, Category wise, Religion wise and Gender wise distribution of population.

Also, the third measure identified on 'Housing Types' where distribution of count of house-types (eg. Flat, Kachha House) is shown state-wise district-wise block-wise area-wise.

Index Terms— Entity Relationship, Document Type Definition, Data Flow Diagram, Use Case Diagram.

I.INTRODUCTION

Tableau is a software that is mainly used for Data Visualization and Business intelligence. It is not necessary to know coding and programming to use tableau. All you really want is a few information and tableau will make dashboards and storyboards from it. The principal component of tableau is it is extremely simple to utilize. In this paper, we are focusing on how E-Governance dashboards can be represented using Tableau software. In this paper, a substantial part of the full-time of the project has been given on the study of Tableau software as it is a relatively new tool in the data analysis field. We have studied about the Data connection, different features of Tableau software, how to extensively use Tableau worksheets, Dashboards and Storyboards and how to prepare any interactive Storyboard using Tableau. After knowing and understanding about the features of Tableau, we have started working on the E-Governance project which includes three measures. The first one is the Geographic measure which mainly deals with different states, districts, blocks and areas. In the second measure that is the Population measure we have dealt with different measures of population (Age-wise, Religion-wise, Category-wise and Gender-wise distribution of population). The third measure or the House-type measure includes distribution of count of house types. After creating these three measures in Tableau, we have represented them in a clear and comprehensible manner using Tableau storyboard, which serves as the project's final phase.

II. PURPOSE

The main purpose of this system is to build a view so that it would be easier to point out the geographic measure and the population measure. With this platform Tableau, we can:

- Build high quality design of the application.
- You do not need any programming knowledge; all you need is information and visualization to create visually engaging reports that tell a story you want to share with your supervisors or impress your teacher in class.
- With its revolutionary drag-and-drop feature, you can effortlessly create stories or reports using just your mouse and a touch of imagination.
- Building a 'Filled Polygon' view with the help of tableau.
- Building a cascading quick filter to create a more generalized view in Tableau.
- Building a proper view of the population measure which will include Age, Category, Gender, Religion using cascading quick filter
- Building similar tableau sheet also for housing measure and also including a cascading quick filter in that.

III. PROPOSED WORK

As there is data available for creation of filled map of any particular state of India, we extended our thoughts of creating district-level, block-level and area-level maps of any particular state of India.

We also thought of creating worksheets which will include different types of population measure and will be helpful in creating storyboard for better understanding of distribution of population in district-wise, block-wise, area-wise manner.

Lastly, we thought of creating a sheet which will show the distribution of population in different house types throughout any particular district, block or area.

After creation of these three sheets, we should plan to attach them in a storyboard. A storyboard is essential for better understanding of the work that any person has done so far. It summarizes the whole system in a proper and user-friendly manner and is effectively used in Tableau projects.

This system has the following functional divisions:

a) Geographic measure

- i) State-wise division
- ii) District-wise division
- iii) Block-wise division
- iv) Area-wise division

b) Population measure

- i) Age-wise division
- ii) Gender-wise division
- iii) Religion-wise division
- iv) Category-wise division

c) Housing measure

- i) House type-wise division

IV FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENTS

The practical prerequisites depict the center usefulness of the application. This part incorporates the information and utilitarian cycle prerequisites.

The main functionality of this system deals with two measures. First one is the Geographical measurement where a district of a particular state is divided into blocks using the 'filled polygon' of Tableau Software. In the second type of measurement, there are another two typical measures where the first one deals with distribution of population (Age wise, Religion wise, Gender wise, Category wise) and the second one is all about Housing.

a) Data Requirements

Dimensions usually generate headers when placed on the rows or columns shelves in a view. Tableau, by default, considers any field with qualitative or categorical data as a dimension, which typically includes fields with text or date values. However, within relational data sources, defining a dimension is a bit more nuanced. A dimension is essentially a field that can be viewed as an independent variable.

When added to the rows or columns shelves, measures typically produce axes. By default, Tableau treats any field containing numeric (quantitative) data as a measure. However, within relational data sources, the actual definition of a measure is more complex. A measure is a field that acts as a dependent variable, meaning its value is influenced by one or more dimensions.

When the information is stacked in the aspect and imprints sheet, first we'll need to bring Point Request from measures sheet to aspect sheet. Following that, we will need to move the Polygon ID, Sub Polygon ID, Point order, district name, and block name to the Marks shelf. And afterward we'll need to drag the scope from measures sheet to lines rack and longitude to segments rack.

Fig.-4.1

V DESIGN OF TABLEAU STORYBOARD AND DASHBOARD

Storyboard:

A story is a sheet that encompasses a collection of worksheets or dashboards working together to convey information. You can create stories to illustrate how facts are connected, provide context, demonstrate the relationship between decisions and outcomes, or simply present a compelling narrative.

A story is a sheet, so the strategies you use to make, name, and in any case oversee worksheets and dashboards apply to stories. Simultaneously, a story is likewise an assortment of sheets, organized in a succession. A "story point" is a specific sheet in a story.

Tableau stories are not just collections of static screenshots; they remain connected to the underlying data and update as the data changes, or as the views and dashboards used in your story change. When you share a story—by, for example, publishing a workbook to Tableau Server or Tableau Online—users can interact with the story to uncover new insights or ask new questions of the data.

There are a wide range of ways of utilizing stories. For instance:

- Use stories for collaborative analysis: You can create stories to compile a sequenced analysis for yourself or to collaborate with colleagues. Perform what-if scenarios or visualize the impact of data changes over time.
- Use stories as show apparatuses: You can utilize stories to introduce a story to a group of people. Similarly as dashboards give spatial plans of perspectives that cooperate, stories present successive courses of action of perspectives or dashboards that make a story stream for your crowd.

There are several ways to build a story. For example, each story point can be based on a different worksheet or dashboard. Alternatively, each story point can be based on a single worksheet or dashboard, which you customize for each point by adding more information as needed. Often, you'll want to combine these approaches, using new sheets for some story points and modifying the same sheet for others.

The Dashboards and Worksheets sheet

In the Dashboards and Worksheets sheet, you can do the following:

- Drag dashboards and worksheets into your story.
- Add a description to a story point.
- Choose to show or hide the navigator buttons.
- Adjust the story size.
- Opt to display the story title.

Fig.-5.1: When district which contains no data is selected

Fig.-5.2: When district which contains data is selected

Fig.-5.3 When any block is selected, corresponding area is automatically selected

Fig.-5.4 When all the blocks are selected, corresponding areas are automatically selected

Fig.-5.5 When any particular point in a Block is selected, also its information could be shown in Tableau using Tooltip

Fig.-5.6 In Geography measure, when the measure 'Age' is selected and along with that, some range is selected

Fig.-5.7 When all age ranges are selected

Fig.-5.8 When any particular range of age in the graph is selected, also its information could be shown in Tableau us

Fig.5.9: When the measure 'Category' is selected, the sub measure also changes

Fig.5.10: When the measure 'Gender' is selected

Fig.5.11: When the measure 'Religion' is selected

Fig.5.12: When measure 'Housing' is selected, but no sub measure is selected

Fig.5.13: When measure 'Housing' is selected along with all the sub measures

VI CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

There are numerous reasons to use Tableau. It's incredibly user-friendly; no programming knowledge is required. With just your data and Tableau, you can create visually appealing reports that effectively convey a story. Whether you're presenting to your directors or impressing your teacher, Tableau empowers you to craft compelling narratives without hassle.

Thanks to its revolutionary drag-and-drop feature, you can effortlessly create stories or reports with just your mouse and a touch of creativity.

This project mainly deals with the Geographic and population measure of a district of West Bengal. With the help of proper data, it could be done for the whole country too. As Tableau is a data analytic tool which is very easy to use and user friendly, it is very useful for the common people who do not know anything about coding.

As we have only worked with data of a particular district of the state West Bengal, there is an opportunity to work with other districts of the state. Furthermore, we can do it for the other states of India as the population distribution would be very easy to understand for the common man.

We have worked only with the population distribution and geographical information. There are also some scopes to work with Food and Water or drainage system of different states and districts of India. The Food measure may include Food production (Crop wise, year wise and block wise) and Food markets per block (Outlets and shops).

Similarly, there are also some scopes to work with Health issues (Insurance coverage, No. of hospitals and beds, Polyclinics and Doctor Slots, Diagnostic center and tests, Medical stores and drugs statistics), Education (No. of primary schools and seats, No. of secondary schools and seats, No. of higher secondary schools and seats, Colleges and seats->degree offered, University and

Seats->degree offered and year wise result), Law and Order of a country (Crime rate per year, No. of cases registered in different Police stations, General Diary and FIRs, Associated Indian Penal Code with these cases, Charge sheet turn-around delay).

We have used Microsoft SQL Server database. If we use Microsoft Office Excel as data-source, it would become easier to upload the data. Also, as data-source, we could have used other databases like MySQL, oracle 10g and so on.

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